

ISic1481

I.Sicily inscription 1481

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Dianae Fons

Place of origin (modern)

Comiso

Provenance

Found in the necropolis of Castiglione

Coordinates

36.950591, 14.649813

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico Ibleo, inventory 5987

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 82 cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. τεῖδε Χοροὶ Κα[τ]
2. ελὸς κεί[ν]ται θα[ν]
3. ἀτοιο λαχόντε
4. ς ἀνφοτέρος δ
5. ἐ καλὸς *ἠ*υιὸς ἔ
6. θαπσε φίλος

Apparatus

Text of Pugliese Carratelli 1942

Translation (en)

Here lie Choro and Katelos, having come to death. Both of them, in fine fashion, their beloved son has buried.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644991
PHI 331215

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Photo J.Prag